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The European Union As An Ideal Model Of Regional Integration: Implications For The Economic Community Of West African States (ECOWAS).

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Abstract

This paper examines the European Union as an exceptional model of regional integration in order to draw out lessons for the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS). The paper delves into the challenges that have bedeviled the smooth operations of ECOWAS as a sub-regional organization. The purpose of the paper is to compare the success story of the EU integration with that of the less success story of ECOWAS. Since the research is exploratory in nature, the Historical/Descriptive approach as a qualitative technique was used in carrying out the study. Documentary instruments such as secondary sources of data was used as the major resource of data collection. Governmental and non-governmental reports, annual reports, expert committees and commission's reports, that deal with the European Union and ECOWAS are compared. It is discovered that external influence from former colonial powers, inadequate institutional capacity, weak harmonization of trade policies and lack of committed political will on the part of the leadership of ECOWAS has hindered the full integration of the sub-region and the formation of a common market. It is also revealing that unlike the EU, which is driven by public opinion and public awareness, there has been how level public awareness creation in ECOWAS. Noteworthy too, ECOWAS has no convertible currency as in the case of Euro for the EU. Remarkably too, unlike the EU, ECOWAS Suffers severe infrastructural deficit.

Key words: ECOWAS, integration, EU, non-governmental, evolutionary

Introduction

The formation of the European Union (EU) has created a historic trend that other regions as well as sub-regional organizations have been trying to emulate. The European Union (EU) has today become a role model of regional integration to other regional international organizations. The European Union (EU) is however not the first experience of European integration. Laursen (2008:3) claims that "Europe was the region of the world where, regional integration started in the early 1950s with the European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC) in 1952". This culminated in the formation of the European Economic Community (EEC) in 1957.

The BBC News World Edition (2011) has chronicled the gradual integration of Europe since 1948. According to the report, the journey towards European integration started sixty six (66) years ago, precisely in 1948 after the Second World War, when, in an attempt to find ways of preventing another war from breaking out, France, Belgium, Luxembourg, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom signed "...the Brussels Treaty agreeing on military assistance, economic, social and cultural cooperation" (BBC News World Edition, 2011). **The spirit behind this treaty was the belief "... that only a supranational organization could eliminate the threat of war between European countries"** (Microsoft Encarta, 2009).

In 1949, they set up the Council of Europe as a forum for all European countries to discuss informal co-operation. In 1951, the same countries implemented what BBC News World Edition (2011) called the Schuman's vision by signing the Treaty of Paris which established the European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC). **The Treaty of Paris came into force in 1954. According to the report, the treaty is so christened because it is based on Robert Schuman, the French Foreign Minister's "... 1950 declaration that coal and steel resources should be pooled to avoid European countries waging war on one another"** (BBC News World Edition, 2011).

The treaty that established the **European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC)** was signed in 1951 and took effect early 1952. "It provided for the elimination of tariffs and quotas on trade in iron ore, coal, coke, and steel within the community; a common external tariff on imports relating to the coal and steel industries from other nations; and controls on production and sales" (Microsoft Encarta, 2009). The treaty established several supranational bodies to supervise operations of the **European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC)**. **These bodies include the high authority,**

which possessed "...executive powers, a council of ministers to safeguard the interests of the member states, a common assembly with advisory authority only, and a court of justice to settle disputes" (Microsoft Encarta, 2009).

Unlike the European Union, ECOWAS also has no long evolutionary history. The idea for a West African community was first conceived by President William Tubman of Liberia in 1964. This culminated in the signing of an agreement by the initial four members; Côte d'Ivoire, Guinea, Liberia and Sierra Leone in February 1965. But quite unfortunately, that agreement did not subsist. The idea for a West African community was revived in April 1972 by General Yakubu Gowon of Nigeria and General Gnassingbe Eyadema of Togo. These two Heads of State embarked on a tour of 12 countries in the sub-region to solicit their plan from July to August 1973 after drawing up proposals. This culminated in the Lomé conference of December 10-15, 1973. The major aim of the Lomé conference was to study the draft treaty for the proposed community. The draft treaty was further examined at a meeting of experts and jurists in Accra, Ghana in January 1974 and later by a ministerial meeting in Monrovia in January 1975. The result was the Treaty of Lagos which was signed on May 28, 1975 by 15 West African countries to establish the Economic Community of West African States. The protocols launching ECOWAS were signed on November 5, 1976 in Lomé, Togo (International Democracy Watch, 2012).

Like the European Union, the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) was established with the goal of enhancing integration among West African States. ECOWAS has a current membership of fifteen (15) member states. These are Benin, Burkina Faso, Cote d'Ivoire, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Togo and Cape Verde. Guinea and Niger are currently on suspension following the 2008 and 2009 coup d'état, respectively.

The EU and ECOWAS both have comparable institutions. For the EU, the key institutions were established 1954. These include the High Authority, which later metamorphosed into the European Commission. Due to Jean Monnet's inspiration for the Schuman declaration, he was elected president of the High Authority. It was Jean Monnet's belief that "...if the nations of Europe were to resume a dominant role in world affairs, they had to speak with one voice and command resources comparable to those of the United States" (Microsoft Encarta, 2009).

The treaty of Paris also established the Common Assembly, which also later metamorphosed into the European Parliament. It also established the Council of Ministers and the Court of Justice. In 1955, the European Defense Community (EDC) treaty was also signed by France, Belgium, Luxembourg, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom in Paris. Unfortunately, after only two years, the European Defense Community (EDC) collapsed. This led to the resignation of Jean Monnet from The High Authority. In 1957 the Treaties of Rome which created the European Atomic Energy Community (Euratom) for the development of peaceful uses of atomic energy and, most important, the European Economic Community (EEC, often referred to as the Common Market) were signed by the participants in the **European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC)**. (Microsoft Encarta, 2009).

On its part, ECOWAS has two major institutions to implement policies - the ECOWAS Commission and the Fund for Cooperation which was later renamed in 2001 as the ECOWAS Bank for Investment and Development. **Other institutions of ECOWAS include** the Secretariat, the Community Court of Justice which was created by the 1991 protocol. The Court of Justice is modeled after the European Court of Human Rights and like the European Court of Human Rights, it has jurisdiction to rule on fundamental human rights breaches. In addition to the above institutions, the 1975 Treaty established four technical and specialized commissions in the fields of trade, customs, immigration, monetary and payments; industry, agriculture and natural resources; transport, telecommunication and energy; and, social and cultural affairs. In 1993, the ECOWAS Treaty was revised to rationalize the aims and objectives of the Community and to improve upon the limitations of the past. The revised Treaty established additional community institutions, namely, the Community Parliament, the Economic and Social Council and the Arbitration Tribunal which was transformed into a full-fledged Community Court of Justice mentioned above (**International Democracy Watch, 2012**).

There have been upheavals in both organizations. For the EU, the challenge came in 1960 when a counter organization, the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) which served as an alternative to the European Economic Community (EEC) was formed by Austria, Denmark, Norway, Portugal, Sweden, Switzerland and the United Kingdom. The European Free Trade Association (EFTA) was the brainchild of the United Kingdom. Arising from her fear of losing control over her domestic policies

which the integration of Europe portended, the United Kingdom persuaded "... other European nations to create a free-trade area instead." (Microsoft Encarta, 2009). Finland, Iceland and Liechtenstein later joined this organisation making it ten members as against the six in the European Economic Community (EEC). Like the European Economic Community (EEC), the aim of the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) was the establishment of free trade in Western Europe. It however differs from the European Economic Community (EEC) in that it "... opposes uniform external tariffs and does not want to put member countries under the authority of supranational institutions" (BBC News World Edition, 2011). It only made provision for the abolition of tariffs on industrial products among member nations. The provision did not cover agricultural products. It did not also provide for a common external tariff. Members were also free to withdraw at any time. This made the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) a very weak organization in comparison to the European Economic Community (EEC). (Microsoft Encarta, 2009). Little wonder it crumbled within a very short space of time.

Eighteen months after the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) was set up, the United Kingdom which was its driving force, applied to join the European Economic Community (EEC). Although the United Kingdom's membership of the European Economic Community (EEC) was vetoed by French President, Charles de Gaulle, twice, 1963 and 1967, it finally became a member of the European Economic Community (EEC). Eventually seven of the ten members of the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) ended up leaving the Association to join the European Economic Community (EEC).

President Charles de Gaulle's veto of the United Kingdom's membership of the European Economic Community (EEC) was not because of her pioneering role in the formation of the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) but because of her close ties with the United States of America.

ECOWAS also had its own share of increase and decrease in membership. For instance, while Cape Verde joined the organization in 1977, Mauritania withdrew from the Community in 2002 (International Democracy Watch, 2012).

1965 marked a watershed in the history of European integration. This year witnessed the signing of the merger Treaty that united the three communities - the European Economic Community, the European Coal and Steel Community, and the European

Atomic Energy Community under the name the European Economic Community (EEC) as the most powerful of the three, and the establishment of a single Council of Ministers and European Commission for the unified communities (BBC News World Edition, 2011). The full merger came in 1967 (Microsoft Encarta, 2009; Europa.com).

In 1973, the European Community was expanded to include Denmark, Ireland and the United Kingdom whose membership was previously vetoed by French President, Charles de Gaulle. This was only possible after the resignation of de Gaulle as French President in 1969 and a more liberal president, Georges Pompidou took over. (Microsoft Encarta, 2009). Pompidou facilitated the creation of "... a permanent financing system for the EC based on contributions from member states; the development of a framework for foreign policy cooperation among member nations; and the opening of membership negotiations with the United Kingdom, Ireland, Denmark, and Norway" through the meeting he scheduled at The Hague in The Netherlands (Microsoft Encarta, 2009).

The British electorate voted to stay in the organization in a referendum two years later, precisely in 1975. On its part, Norwegian membership was stalled by a referendum of her citizens in 1972.

In May 1972, at the end of the Bretton Woods (adjustable-peg) system, many countries in Western Europe attempted to stabilize their currencies in relation to each other's currencies. "The arrangements known as the Snake in the Tunnel (or, more frequently, as the Snake), which were set up by members of the European Economic Community (EEC) lasted until 1979. Each member agreed to limit, by market intervention, the fluctuations of its currency's exchange rate in terms of other members' currencies. The maximum divergence between the strongest and the weakest currencies was 2.25%." The agreement meant that the French government, for example, would ensure that the value of the French franc show very limited fluctuation in terms of the currencies of other members of the group. This commitment was not however extended to currencies of countries outside the agreement (Mushin 2010:1).

In 1979, the Commission's President Roy Jenkins, introduced the European Monetary System (EMS) thus setting Europe on the road towards the euro. The European Monetary System (EMS) is made up of the European Currency Unit (Ecu)

and the Exchange Rate Mechanism (ERM). The European Currency Unit (Ecu) which was originally a unit for the community's internal budget later took on some of the characteristics of a real currency and was used in instruments like travelers' cheques and bank deposits. The European Currency Unit (Ecu) is also the denomination for the Exchange Rate Mechanism (ERM) which itself is "... a system which gives national currencies a central exchange rate against the European Currency Unit (Ecu). Each currency can fluctuate above and below this rate within certain boundaries" (BBC News World Edition, 2011). Since then, all the members of the European Economic Community (EEC) joined the Exchange Rate Mechanism (ERM), except the United Kingdom. It was also in 1979 that Europeans voted in the first direct elections to the European Parliament.

Statement of the Research Problem

Since the establishment of the ECOWAS in 1975 and the EU in 1993, both have received research works on the rationale, structure, policy implantation and performance assessment, mindful of the fact that ECONAS has less success history than the EU. Though several research works have been done on the ECOWAS and the EU respectively, less attention seemed to have been on what comparative lessons open to ECOWAS on the EU success story of integration. This apparent gap in knowledge drives this research problematic.

Aim:

The main aim of this research effort is the comparatives examine lessons open to ECOWAS in the study of the EU integration success story.

Literature Review:

Some writers on ECOWAS like Claeys and Sindzingre (2003) belief that many regional initiatives have been inspired by the European Union experience in terms of policy agenda and institutional development. They particularly identified the extent to which the West African Economic and Monetary Union also known in French as *Union Économique et Monétaire Ouest-Africaine* (UEMOA) attempts to imitate some of the norms the European Monetary Union. In spite of this, James (1993), Asiwaju (2008) and Higgott (2005) have doubted the strength of ECOWAS integrating process, noting that a number of growing challenges have not given the integrating process the much required fast momentum. Among other things, they have identified unequal income distribution among member states which creates tensions within the community as one of the challenges to the integration process. On

his part, Adedeji (2002) has identified the proliferation of sub-regional groupings in Africa as another potential hindrance to the successful integration of the West African sub-region under ECOWAS.

Among all the writers on integration in the Third World, Abutudu (1988) seems to capture the major problem hindering full integration of the West African sub-region under ECOWAS. Writing from the dependency perspective, his writing elucidates the incapability of Less Developed Countries (LDCs), ECOWAS member countries in this case, carrying out effective regional integration due to the dislocation in their national economies since trade, aid and investment comes from their former colonial masters. The impact of these dislocations, according to him, is assumed to be too much for individual economies to bear, hence the need for a collective action to "ameliorate the effects of the national disengagement process by replacing North-South vertical relations with South-South horizontal relations UDCs" (Abutudu, 1988:38).

Unfortunately, the possibility of the envisaged collective action has been stalled due to weak currencies and chronic budget deficits which most of the WAMZ's countries suffer from. This, according to International Democracy Watch (2012), is what has delayed the proposed merger of the CFA franc and Eco, in order to give all of West and Central Africa a single stable currency.

This has stimulated some questions that will guide this study.

1. Is there any possibility for countries in the West African sub-region, like their counterparts in the European Union (EU), to be effectively integrated under the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS)?
2. What are the hindrances to the success of the integration process of ECOWAS member countries?

Theoretical Framework:

This study was carried out using Integration Theory as a framework. Integration, as the name implies, is the process of integrating two or more previously autonomous political entities into unity. In other words, it is the process of merging previously independent political units to form one larger unit. Integration therefore is a process of turning "... previously separate units into a coherent system" (Deutsch, 1989:212). Haas (1958) in his classic, *The Uniting of Europe* as quoted by Laursen, (2008:4) defined integration as "...the process whereby political actors in several distinct national settings are persuaded to shift their loyalties, expectations and political

activities to a new center whose institutions possess or demand jurisdiction over the pre-existing national states.”

Integration can be seen as an international phenomenon. According to Castaneda (2006:1), international integration is “... a process by which countries remove the barriers to free trade and the free movement of people across national borders, with the goal of reducing the tensions that can lead to international conflict”. Lindberg in his, *The Political Dynamics of European Economic Integration*, also quoted by Laursen (2008:4) defined political integration firstly as “...the process whereby nations forgo the desire and ability to conduct foreign policy and key domestic policies independently of each other, seeking instead to make joint decisions or to delegate the decision-making process to new central organs” and secondly as “... the process whereby political actors in several distinct settings are persuaded to shift their expectations and political activities to a new center.”

On his part, Deutsch (1957) as quoted in Laursen (2008:4) defined integration as “the attainment within a territory, of a 'sense of community' and of institutions and practices strong enough and widespread enough to assure, for a 'long' time, dependable expectations of 'peaceful change' among its population.” The result of the integration process is the formation of a “security community” (Laursen, 2008:4). Integration could be differentiated from amalgamation. Amalgamation, according to Deutsch, is “the formal merger of two or more previously independent units into a single larger unit, with some type of common government” (Laursen, 2008:4). Integration brings about such interconnectedness that results in a system with some special properties and behaviour which the different units could not have produced independently. This, according to him produces such cohesion that enables the integrated system to “... withstand stress and strain, support and equilibrium, and resist disruptions” (Deutsch, 1989:212-213). Deutsch believes the cohesion of any integrated system is determined by the amount of strain it has survived. Collective decision-making is an important aspect of all regional integration efforts (Laursen (2008:4). Central to Linberg's definition above is “the development of devices and processes for arriving at collective decisions by means other than autonomous action by national governments” (Laursen, 2008:4).

It is David Mitrany that nonetheless gave a deeper insight into what integration is all about. Mitrany's postulations in the late 1940s were undoubtedly influenced by the rapid growth of modern corporations in the industrialized world (Popoviciu, 2010:1). Mitrany was preoccupied with changing the attitudes of states in matters that

transcend national boundaries with the aim of achieving social peace and prosperity. His postulates, which came to be known as "functionalism" (although he himself did not use this term) were propositions for a new international order based on transnational cooperation. Although some scholars have argued that Mitrany is not the first to develop the functional approach to international cooperation, his postulations nevertheless laid the ground work for both regional and international integration efforts today. "Writing in a period in which Europe was confronting profound crisis, Mitrany managed to offer to the functionalist theory arguments for global but also regional integration" (Popoviciu, 2010:1).

Mitrany's main concern was how European states could efficiently manage the limited resources as a nexus for "... durable cooperation and for creating of what he defined as being a working peace system" (Popoviciu, 2010:1). Mitrany's functionalism therefore became a generating paradigm of economic, social and also political cohesion in international relations and European integration agenda.

Afraid that the trend in nationalist self-determination of the late 40s will destroy the international division of labour that welded peoples and countries together globally, Mitrany recommended international unification either in the form of "(i) a general and fairly loose association, like the League of Nations and the United Nation, (ii) a federal system and (iii) functional arrangements" (Mitrany, 1948:350). He blamed the ineffectiveness of the League of Nations as well as the United Nations on the problem of national exclusivism. This, according to him, is what made the defunct League of Nations and its successor, the United Nations to become

loose associations for occasional specific joint action, in regard to each of which each member remains on the whole free to participate or not. They are clubs which make joint action easier, if wanted, and in the United Nations facilities for economic and social action are improved; but they cannot prescribe action, much less take it on their own authority (Mitrany, 1948:351).

Due to the ineffectiveness of such a loose organization like the United Nations to effectively coordinate international interaction, Mitrany agreed with some scholars that international federalism, or what he called "European federation or Western federation or democratic federation or, more ambitiously, world federation", would be a better arrangement that could work for Western Europe (Mitrany, 1948:351). However, due to the rigidity inherent in a federal arrangement, Mitrany prescribed the

functional approach which has been successfully applied in established federations (Mitrany, 1948:354).

He cited the successful building of the Alcan highway from the United States through Canada to Alaska through transnational cooperation between the United States and Canada and the development of the Rio Grande through the cooperation of the United States and Mexico as pointers to the possibility of international unification (Mitrany, 1948:355-356). Mitrany also believe that the success of the "wartime functional arrangement" and the workings of the International Labour Organisation are pointers to the possibility of successful international functional collaboration (Mitrany, 1948:357).

The establishment of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) set the pace for the integration of all the countries in the West African sub-region. The effectiveness of the integration process under ECOWAS would result in Castaneda's (2006:3) belief that as states integrate in limited functional, technical, and/or economic areas, the interdependence will result in the development of its own internal dynamics by the system and the resultant satisfaction of human needs by the functional agencies would "... attract the loyalty of the populations and stimulate their participation and expand the area of integration."

The starting point of integration is usually a free trade area, followed by a customs union, a common market, and then the integration of monetary and fiscal matters to establish an economic union (Mubarik, 2014). ECOWAS has been able to pass some of these phases, therefore it can be said to be set for integration.

Research Questions

1. What are the institutional mechanisms employed by the ECOWAS and the EU?
2. What are the strategies adopted by the ECOWAS and the EU to drive policy objectives?
3. What are the challenges confronting ECOWAS in achieving its policy objectives?
4. Are there prospects of the ECOWANS achieving comparative success story as the EU?

Research Objectives

The research objectives are:

1. to determine the nature of institutional capacity mechanisms of the ECOWAS and the EU;
2. to attempt a comparative evaluation of implementation strategies adopted by the ECOWAS and the EU on policy objectives;
3. to identify challenges militating against the ECOWAS in achieving its policy objectives;
4. to make further recommendations on the policy and strategy direction of the ECOWAS.

Research Hypotheses:

In order to properly situate this study on the European Union as an Ideal Model of Regional Integration: Implications for the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), the following hypothesis were formulated to guide the study.

- Hypothesis 1:** The influence of the former colonial powers greatly reduces the ability of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) from effectively integrating the countries in the West African sub-region.
- Hypothesis 2:** Inadequate institutional capacity hinders the integration process of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS)
- Hypothesis 3:** Lack of harmonized monetary policies between the Anglophone and Francophone ECOWAS member countries has a negative impact on the integration process of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS).
- Hypothesis 4:** Lack of political will on the part of the leadership of ECOWAS hinders the integration process of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS).

Method of Research

This study which seeks to investigate the effectiveness of ECOWAS in integrating the countries in the West African sub-region after the European Union model is a

qualitative research. Therefore, Historical/Descriptive approach was used as the research method in carrying out the study. According to Biereenu-Nnabugwu (2006:104), historical research is one of the six types of research designs when classified according to the "... dominant method of data collection contained in the design." On its part, Encyclopedia Britannica online (2010), states that "the traditional descriptive-historical approach to the study of writing is by far the most common. This is a simple narrative approach to the description of writing in its historical evolution." According to Barbie and Morton (2001:30), the main purpose of descriptive research is to observe and describe situations and events. Descriptive studies are known for providing information for planning and program implementation as well as make between groups (Araoye, 2003:55).

Since the research is exploratory in nature, the Historical and Descriptive approach as a qualitative technique is best suited for the work because it enhanced the use of documentary data to evaluate the organization under study. The Historical and Descriptive approach is mainly a situation analysis of the phenomena to be investigated. It has no comparative or control experiment to identify the data which account for the current state of the phenomenon, that is, describe what exists and the variables responsible for their existence. It investigates the phenomenon and describes it as it is. The Historical and Descriptive research assumes the form of a narrative which gives a prima facie account of observable facts without complicating information. Historical and descriptive research interprets past trends of attitude, events, and facts. In a more explicit manner, historical and descriptive research may be considered as embracing the whole field of human past as broad as life itself (Osuala, 2005:56). In the context of this study, the methodology involves the description of the impact of Western influence on the process of integration in the West African sub-region under ECOWAS.

The data sought for was therefore obtained from a library based investigation. As the nature of descriptive studies is, this study aimed at finding out "what is". In this context therefore, exploratory method was used to collect descriptive data used in analyzing the effect of the external influence on ECOWAS integration process.

Discussion:

Although ECOWAS has been able to establish a customs union and a common market, it still has the problem of monetary and fiscal integration that would have resulted in the establishment of an economic union. This is due to the multiplicity of

currencies and exchange rate changes among the member countries. This problem has hindered full integration of the member states. To address this problem, ECOWAS has been carrying out "currency convertibility and monetary integration activities" (Ogunkola, 2005:1). As member countries implement structural adjustment programs (SAPs), it has resulted in a reasonable level of convergence, although a real exchange rate (RER) has not yet been achieved. Ogunkola (2005:1) has shown that "...wide differences still exist between RER shocks facing CFA zone and non-CFA zone West African countries."

The possibility of closing of this gap between the CFA zone and non-CFA zone is debatable because of the fact that while the CFA franc exchange rate is tied to that of the euro and guaranteed by the French Treasury, as mentioned above, the WAMZ is not. A detachment of the CFA franc from the euro, and consequently, from France is necessary to fast track the monetary integration of ECOWAS member countries. Unfortunately, this may take a longer time due to the close tie and high dependence of the countries in the CFA zone to France, their former colonial power as well as the dependence of the WAMZ countries on Britain. The need for more convergence in economic policy and RER between the CFA zone and non-CFA zone therefore cannot be over emphasized. Moreover, alternatives to dependence on the former colonial powers in monetary and economic matters is necessary for an effective monetary union in West Africa.

Since inception, ECOWAS has not been able to institute of a customs union and common external tariff that cuts across both the CFA zone and non-CFA zone. Only the CFA zone has a customs union and operates common external tariff regime. Where the organization operates a customs union and common external tariff across the two zones, the integration process will be greatly enhanced.

In structure, ECOWAS institutions, unlike European Union institutions do not possess the capacity to foster speedy integration of the West African sub-region. Unlike the European Union which is structured as a sovereign state and operates through a multi-system of supranational independent institutions which include the European Commission, the Council of the European Union, the European Council, the Court of Justice of the European Union, and the European Central Bank, the institutions of ECOWAS are not adequate and do not possess the peremptory authority like the above-mentioned institutions of the European Union.

For instance, the ECOWAS Commission which is the center of the organization's administration and which is involved in almost every aspect of ECOWAS affairs does not have the same authority like the European Commission. Although the Commission, since replacing the Secretariat, has been moderately successful in its role of facilitating, coordinating and monitoring the implementation of the community's programmes and in recommending and initiating programmes of political cooperation such as trade or migration policies. And also in implementing the ECOWAS protocol on free movement of goods and persons has been incapacitated due to ineffective coordination of policies, inadequate finance and inadequate skilled personnel which it inherited from the Secretariat. Quoting Asante (2012), Mubarik (2013:5) has shown that "the inadequacy of human capacity at the Commission has been compounded by the lack of training programmes to update the skills and enhance the productivity of existing staff, especially professionals whose fields are characterized by rapid advancement of knowledge. Choosing the head of Commission has been based on a predictable rotational system rather than strictly on competence." This is one of the problems that has impaired the integration process in ECOWAS.

Findings:

From the study, it has been discovered that external influence from former colonial powers has greatly affected the integration effort of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) in the long run. The formation of a separate monetary union, the *Union Économique et Monétaire Ouest-Africaine* (UEMOA) by the Francophone component of ECOWAS on the inspiration of France and the establishment of the West African Monetary Zone (WAMZ) in 2000 by the Anglophone components of ECOWAS is proof of the hypothesis that the influence of the former colonial powers tends to greatly reduce the ability of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) from effectively integrating the countries in the West African sub-region.

This study also shows that unlike the European Union, ECOWAS lacks adequate institutional capacity to bring about the integration of its member states. Unlike the European Union institutions, the institutions of ECOWAS are not adequate and do not possess the peremptory authority like the institutions of the European Union. This proves the hypothesis that inadequate institutional capacity seems to be one of the hindrances to the integration process of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS).

The study also discovered that with different monetary unions covering the Francophone countries and the Anglophone countries, respectively, the monetary policies of ECOWAS countries are not harmonized and therefore, the possibility of full integration is slim. This validates the hypothesis that lack of harmonized monetary policies between the Anglophone and Francophone ECOWAS member countries may greatly slow down the integration process of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) in the long run.

Finally, unlike the leadership of the European Union that require members to surrender their sovereignty to the Union and compel compliance to the policies of the organization, the leadership of ECOWAS depend on the voluntary cooperation of its members. And unlike the European Union (EU) which is an federated union in the process of becoming a supranational organization and in line with supranationalism, the European Commission controls most of the important decisions and resists member countries that adopt policies that undermine full integration, neither the ECOWAS Parliament nor the Economic and Social Council can resist member countries that adopt policies that undermine the integration process of the Union. This validates the hypothesis that lack of political will on the part of the leadership of ECOWAS tends to hinder the integration process of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS).

Conclusion And Recommendation

It is the conclusion of this study that the European Union is the most effective example of regional integration. To be effective in its integration effort therefore, ECOWAS should imitate the European Union integration model. This study has proven without doubt that ECOWAS is still very far from implementing the European model of integration as epitomized by the European Union. This is due to external influence from former colonial powers, inadequate institutional capacity, lack of harmonized trade policies and lack of political will on the part of the leadership of ECOWAS.

The study therefore recommends that ECOWAS member countries must take a cue from the European Union by showing more commitment to the body in order to strengthen sectoral integration in the sub-region. It is also recommended that ECOWAS should strengthen the deficiencies in the institutions of the sub-regional body and the harmonization of trade policies among member countries. Like the EU,

ECOWAS must begin a process of gradual elimination of import duties and quotas on all trade between member nations and institute a common external tariff. ECOWAS member nations must also agree to implement common policies regarding transportation, agriculture, and social insurance, and to permit unfettered free movement of people and financial resources within the boundaries of the community. Provisions of the ECOWAS Treaty must be revised to give some supranational character to the organization and ensure that no member nation could unilaterally renounce the treaty or breach the organizations' protocols with impunity.

Finally, ECOWAS member countries should break from the apron-string of their former colonial masters and implement a collective self reliance in order to promote autonomus development of the region.

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